

Electro-osmotic Experiments on Intensity of Adsorption of a Constituent Ion by an Insoluble Salt.

Part I.

BY

JNANENDRA NATH MUKHERJEE

AND

HIRA LAL RAY.

A heteropolar precipitate like that of an insoluble salt has a tendency to adsorb its constituent ions from aqueous solutions. It seems that this type of adsorption is responsible for several phenomena which do not at first sight appear to be correlated. Lottermoser observed that precipitated silver salts pass into the colloidal state when the solution contains one of the common ions in excess. The charge of the colloid is of the same sign as that of the constituent ion which is present in excess in the solution. Marc from his experiments on the adsorption by crystalline surfaces [*Z. phys. Chem.*, 75, 710 (1911); 81, 641 (1913)] concluded that a crystalline substance adsorbs only those dissolved substances which can form isomorphous compounds with the crystal or compounds which have similar crystalline forms. Fajans and Beer [*Ber.*, 46, 3486 (1913); also 48, 700 (1915)] pointed out that the separation of a radio-element from its solution by an insoluble salt takes place only when the radio-element itself can form an insoluble precipitate. Paneth and Horowitz [(*Z. Phys. Chem.* 89, 513, (1915); also

Phys. Z. 15, 924 (1914)] recognised in view of Marc's work that the separation of radio-elements, by precipitates is due to the adsorption of the radio-element, and that a radio-element will be adsorbed by an insoluble heteropolar adsorbent only when it can form an insoluble salt. Paneth however, considers that the adsorption of the radio-element consists in an actual exchange of places between ions in the crystal lattice and the radio-elements in solution. Thus barium ions in barium sulphate are replaced by radium ions from solution and the barium ions pass into solution.

It has been pointed out by the writer that in the case of a large number of colloidal suspensoids, the stabilising electrolyte has an ion in common with the colloid, and that the adsorption of a common ion by a precipitate is a simple consequence of the modern view of the structure of crystals of salts. (Far. Soc. Disc. October, 1920; published October, 1921.) The adsorption of an ion imparts a charge to the surface and thus tends to peptise the precipitate. It has been further pointed out (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*; Phil. Mag., 1922, VI, 44, p. 327) that there is an essential difference in the manner of adsorption as pictured by Paneth and that which must be assumed to account for the stability of colloids. The type of adsorption suggested by Paneth will not impart a charge to the surface and hence cannot account either for the observations on the charge of colloids in the presence of peptising electrolytes or for their stability. The exchange of ions between the crystal lattice and the solution must be a slow process, when the salt is only sparingly soluble, whereas the adsorption of ions by the surface will be much quicker. Both types of adsorption have probably to be taken into account, but it appears

from the literature on colloids that the adsorption of ions as such by the surface is more frequent than an actual interchange of ions as conceived by Paneth. Experimental evidence will be adduced in the sequel in support of this view.

Another class of phenomena is also probably closely connected with the adsorption of constituent ions by a precipitate. Bradford [(*Biochem. J.* ; 10, p. 169 (1916), 11, p. 14 (1917)] has suggested that the adsorption of the precipitating ions is at least partly responsible for the formation of Liesegang rings. The adsorption of constituent ions may also affect the permeability of the precipitate to the diffusing ions—a factor which also probably plays an important role in the formation of Liesegang rings. (Fischer, *Koll. Zeit.* 30, 1920, p. 13.)

The experiments of Debye and Scherrer have shown that colloidal particles have the same crystalline structure as they have in large masses or well-developed crystals. One has, of course, to remember that the surface forces acting on constituent ions existing in the solution are not exactly similar to those acting on the ion in the interior of the lattice. (Madelung, *Phys. Z.* 20, 494, 1919). But such considerations do not materially affect the validity of our point of view.

Fajans and Beckerath (*Z. Phys. Chem.* 97, 1921, 478) have suggested an explanation similar to ours regarding the adsorption of a constituent ion by a crystal lattice. They have further attempted to consider the energy required to separate an adsorbed ion from the surface in the light of the work necessary to separate the constituent ions from the crystal lattice and the energy change due to hydration. These authors consider that there is a close relationship between the

intensity of adsorption of the ions by the surface and the solubility of the corresponding salt (*loc. cit.*, p. 500). Langmuir (J. Amer. Chem. Soc. 38 (1916) 2221; 39, 1917, 1848), considers the intensity of adsorption to be determined by the energy changes associated with the process. So far no very definite result has been obtained from this treatment as the energy changes associated with the process of adsorption do not admit of easy theoretical calculation and the estimates of the energy change are based on more or less arbitrary assumptions. It would appear from the sequel that Fajans's method of treatment is too simple to account for the intensity of adsorption of ions.

The present investigation deals with the adsorption of ions by precipitated and carefully washed lead chromate. This substance was selected because it has been used in many cases for the investigation of Liesegang rings. Moreover there is a large number of insoluble lead salts and it is of interest to compare the relative intensity of adsorption of different anions by a surface of lead chromate with the solubility products of the corresponding salt.

The amounts of ions adsorbed has been mostly measured from chemical analysis, or from measurements of activity where the sensitive radio-active methods can be used. These methods do not give any indication as to whether the adsorbed ions replace those of the same sign in the crystal lattice thus leaving the crystal and its surface electrically neutral or are adsorbed on the surface with or without exchange of ions and the surface becomes electrically charged, through an excess in the adsorption of ions of one sign. Electro-osmotic measurements can decide between these two possibilities. Moreover, it is more convenient and accurate than analytical methods. It may be noted here that recently several investigators

have emphasized the necessity of considering simultaneous adsorption of the solvent and of the solute. The analytical result represents the net effect. One cannot therefore simply say that so much of the solute has been adsorbed. In fact some assumptions about the relative adsorptions of the solute and the solvent have to be made in order that an actual idea of the adsorption of the solute can be made (*cf.* Wo. Ostwald and Izagguire, *Koll. Z.* 80, 1919, 279, also previous literature). Of course it is possible that for the dilute solutions with which we are dealing, the adsorption of the solvent can be assumed to be more or less constant. But if there be alterations in hydration, on the adsorption of ions consequent on the variation in the electric charge, then we have a fresh source of disturbance and analytical data do not give a clear idea of the adsorption.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The arrangement used for the electro-osmotic measurements is a modified form of that used by Briggs the straight tube being replaced by a U-tube which does away with the use of porous plugs or glasswool (*cf.* Mukherjee, *Nature*, Dec. 2, 1922). The method gives results accurate within $\pm 7\%$. The position of the electrodes in the U-tube did not vary during these experiments. The same U-tube and the glass tube connections were used throughout these experiments. The U-tube was always filled with the precipitated lead chromate between two marks symmetrically placed one on each limb of the U-tube. The precipitate was stirred with water or electrolyte and then poured in the U-tube and allowed to settle for 24 hours. The excess of lead chromate was drawn off with a pipette. The thickness of the layer of the precipitate was 12.8 cm. The preparation

and purification of the precipitate requires great care. Chemically pure lead nitrate was further purified by recrystallisations. The crystals were powdered and dried at 102° . Chemically pure potassium chromate was carefully washed in a Buchner funnel. Two solutions of lead nitrate and potassium chromate of equal strength were prepared and lead-chromate was precipitated by addition of equivalent amounts of the two solutions from a burette into a beaker with silver nitrate as outside indicator.

The supernatant liquid was poured out and the precipitate was digested in pure boiling water for half an hour and the supernatant liquid was again poured out. The finer particles were removed along with the supernatant liquid. The process was repeated 10-12 times. It appears that potassium chromate was adsorbed in perceptible quantities during the precipitation, though the supernatant liquid after precipitation showed no trace of chromate with silver nitrate. During the first two digestions, the supernatant liquid assumed a yellow colour after some time, but in subsequent washings remained quite colourless. The substance becomes more free from adsorbed chemicals with repeated digestions. The digested and wet lead chromate was kept in stoppered resistance glass bottles in a place free from fumes.

Differences in the size of the air bubble within fair limits do not influence its velocity for the same experimental arrangement.

Every experiment was carried out under exactly similar conditions. The electric current is switched on for five minutes and the tube is then allowed to rest till the air-bubble becomes stationary, and the distance the bubble has moved is noted. The direction of the current is then reversed, and the mean of the two readings is taken. This was repeated at least five times in each case and their

mean was taken. The different readings do not differ by more than $\pm 5\%$.

When electrolytes were used, the same amount of the precipitate was washed with the electrolyte solution several times to ensure that the concentration of electrolyte taken remains unchanged after removal of the water and after adsorption. The results are given below. The method is not free from certain sources of error and it is intended to investigate them with a view to modify the experimental arrangements. It may be added that the usual method is sufficiently accurate for our present purpose.

At high electrolyte concentrations the acids set free on electrolysis of the salt solution convert the chromate into dichromate with the consequent change in colour.

The velocity of the bubble is proportional to the density of the electrical charge on the surface. Since

$$v^* = \frac{e \cdot H \cdot q \cdot \delta}{\eta}$$

where v = velocity in cms/sec (of the bubble).

H = pot. grad ent.

q = sectional area.

e = density of electrical charge; δ = the thickness of the double layer and η = co-efficient of viscosity.

H and q are constant under the conditions of the experiment. η may be taken to be constant for these dilute salt solutions, and δ is assumed to be constant.

* We have taken the usual form of the equation cf. (Freundlich, *Kapillarchemie*, 1922, p. 329).

TABLE I.

*Lead Chromate.*Velocity in cm. per sec. \times 300.

Electrolytic concn	Water	KCl	K ₂ CrO ₄	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	KNO ₃	K ₂ SO ₄	BaCl ₂	KI	KIO ₃	CaCl ₂
0	18.2									
N/15000		22.0								
N/5000		23.0	25.1	7.1	20.2	22.6	20.2	22.7	26.6	21.4
N/4000		26.6								
N/2500		28.1								
N/2000		29.8	35.3	-3	31.3	32	20.7	30.5	32.5	25.5
N/1000		32.4	44.9	-7.9	32.8	38.5	17.5	Decomposition sets in	36.3	25.5
N/500		36.8					14.3			
N/250		Decomposition sets in								

DISCUSSION

The readings with water alone show that the substance is negatively charged in contact with water. We are not sure whether the negative charge owes its origin to the adsorption of chromate ions which probably could not be removed even after 13 digestions with pure boiling water, or to the adsorption of hydroxyl ions from water.* It will be seen from the above that of the four cations, K, Ba, Pb and Ca, only Pb⁺⁺ ions materially affect the velocity of the bubble, diminishing it markedly at as low a concentration as n/5000 and at a higher concentration n/1000, the bubble moves in the opposite direction.

* The question will be dealt with in a second communication.

These experiments bring out undoubtedly that the adsorption of the positively charged lead ion at first decreases the density of the negative charge on the surface till at a higher concentration, the surface positively becomes charged being covered with an excess of lead ions. It would have been of great interest to follow the the increase in charges still further with increasing concentration, but the transformation of chromate unfortunately prevents further observation.

The marked adsorption of the lead ions in contrast to that of the other cations can be readily understood if we remember that it is a constituent ion of the precipitate (*cf.* Mukherjee, *Far. Soc. Disc.* Oct. 1922 ; *Phil. Mag.*, *loc. cit.*).

A comparison of the effects of K, Ba or Ca will show that for the same anion, Ba⁺⁺ ions are more adsorbed than Ca⁺⁺ ions and that K⁺ ions are least adsorbed.

On the other hand, of the anions the chromate which is the other constituent ion has a great effect on the charge. In general, on the addition of an electrolyte other than the lead salt, there is an increase in the negative charge to begin with. In the case of BaCl₂ the charge at first remains constant up to a concentration of N/2000 and then begins to decrease. This is a very common feature of the curves between the charge and the concentration of the electrolyte, when the oppositely charged ion is weakly adsorbed (*cf.* Mukherjee, *Phil. Mag.* VI, 44, 1922, pp. 328 *et. seq.*). In the case of CaCl₂ the anion effect predominates within the limits of concentration studied, the density of the charge being always greater than that with pure water. The cation effect is however apparent if we compare the relative

effects of calcium chloride, potassium nitrate and potassium chloride.

A quantitative comparison of the relative intensities of adsorption of individual ions is not easy. The observations show that adsorption of both ions at these low concentrations has to be considered. For the different potassium salts it is permissible to compare the relative anion effects, as the cation is the same in each case. In comparing the intensities of the adsorption of the anions, the valency of the anion has to be taken into account. For the same increase in the density of the negative charge, the amount of an anion adsorbed is inversely proportional to its valency. Since we know the valency and the increase in the densities of the charge compared to that for pure water, we can compare the relative amounts of the different anions adsorbed. Such a comparison is however not free from objections. First of all, the assumption (*loc. cit.*) of a constant thickness of the double layer is not certainly self-evident. Secondly, we do not know exactly the source of the charge of the surface in contact with water and a replacement of the ions already existing on the surface by the ions of the same charge present in the solution, will not alter the charge and will escape detection. Consequently, even if adsorption takes place there may be no alteration in the charge. The error due to this cause will however be smaller, when the change in charge is great. For this reason, we have taken the values at $\cdot 0005N$ for comparison. Probably the initial charge is due to the adsorption of chromate ions as it is almost impossible to remove the last traces of adsorbed electrolytes by washing or by digestion with boiling water in many cases. The only other source may be the adsorption of hydroxyl

ions from water. Lastly the variation in the charge is due to the adsorption of two ions of opposite sign and it is evidently erroneous to refer all of the observed difference to the adsorption of one ion only. These objections are not likely to influence the general nature of the conclusions we have drawn from the comparison outlined above. Since we have at present no idea as to what determines the thickness of the double layer, we might leave it out of account, though it is probable that the thickness of the double layer depends on the density of the electrical charge. This is justifiable to some extent on the ground, that so far conclusions drawn from the assumption, that the velocity of electro-osmosis, or cataphoresis is proportional to the density of the electrical charge on the surface, have helped us consistently to explain colloidal phenomena associated with electrical charge of particles. Regarding the last objection we might neglect the adsorption of the weakly adsorbed ion, in comparison to that of the other as a first approximation, as the great change in the charge shows the preponderating effect of the one over that of the other. In order to form an idea of the relative intensity of adsorption, we must compare the amounts of the anions adsorbed at the same gm. anion concentration. The difference in the velocity is proportional to the net amount of positive or negative charge adsorbed in the form of ions (of both sign) per unit surface. If we compare the potassium salts, we may assume the adsorption of the cation to be constant and the increase in the velocity (*i. e.* of the negative charge) is then proportional to the number of ions adsorbed, multiplied by its valency. The amount of the different anions adsorbed is then given by the increase in velocity (referred to the value for water) divided by the valency of the anion. The following table shows

the values for a concentration of $\cdot 0005$ gm. anion per litre.

TABLE II.

Potassium Salts.

Anions.	Conc. in gm. ions per litre.	Difference in velocity	Valency	Amount adsorbed
Cl'	$\cdot 0005$	29·8-18·2	1	11·6
NO ₃ '	$\cdot 0005$	31·3-18·2	1	13·1
SO ₄ '	$\cdot 0005$	38·5-18·2	2	$\frac{20·3}{2} = 10·15$
CrO ₄ '	$\cdot 0005$	44·9-18·2	2	$\frac{23·7}{2} = 11·85$
I'	$\cdot 0005$	30·5-18·2	1	12·3
IO ₃ '	$\cdot 0005$	32·5-18·2	1	14·3

The anions arrange themselves in the following order:—

The order given above does not exactly represent the *relative* intensities of adsorption for anions of different valency. The adsorption of chromate and sulphate ions must be greater than that indicated above for two reasons.

(1) Now the velocity of osmosis indicates the net negative charge being the actual charge due to the adsorbed anions less the charge due to the fixed layer of cations. Since we are comparing equal gram-anion concentrations, the concentration of cation will be double for the divalent anions of what it is for univalent anions. The adsorption of the cations is not negligible and the amount of cation adsorbed at the higher concentration will be greater. So that the same velocity

of movement of the bubble at equal gram-anion concentration would indicate a higher adsorption of divalent anions than of univalent anions, or in other words more chromate and sulphate ions are actually adsorbed than are represented by the figures 13.35 and 10.15.

(2) Secondly the density of the negative charge (44.9) for chromate ion is much greater than that in the case of iodate ions (32.5) and the greater negative charge diminishes to a greater extent the number of collision of the anions on the 'charge. The adsorption of an ion depends on the intensity of adsorption, *i.e.*, on the energy change associated with the process of adsorption by a neutral surface and on the number of collisions on the surface. In the case where we are dealing with the adsorption of ions, carrying an electrical charge of the same sign as that of the adsorbing surface, the number of collisions evidently do not depend on the concentration of the anion. Only those ions can strike on the surface which have sufficient kinetic energy to overcome the electrical repulsion when it approaches the surface. The greater, the negative charge of the surface, the fewer the collisions of the anion on the surface as compared to the probable number of collisions if the surface were neutral. The greater negative charge of the solid in contact with potassium chromate makes the further adsorption of chromate ions more difficult than in the case of the iodate ions of the same gram-anion concentration. If the electrical conditions were identical, the adsorption of the chromate ions would have been greater than that indicated above. We may therefore take the order to be

which is also the order of the increasing solubilities of the

lead salts expressed in terms of gr. atomic concentration of lead,

with the exception of the nitrate.

A strict comparison between the order of adsorbability and of solubility is therefore not possible. Further solubility of the corresponding salt is not a measure of the change in energy when an ion passes from the adsorbed layer in the surface to the solution. For the same reason, a comparison of the lattice energy and of the intensity of adsorption is also not possible without further assumptions regarding the energy of hydration and regarding the effect of adsorption on the hydration of the ion and on the hydration of the surface (Fajans, *loc. cit.*). We, therefore think that Fajans's conclusions as to the relationship between solubility and intensity of adsorption are untenable. It is however remarkable that the order for the other anions is practically the same as that suggested by Fajans.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS.

It is possible to draw certain definite conclusions from the experiments recorded here.

(1) A well-digested precipitate of lead chromate is not electrically neutral against water. The negative charge is probably due to the adsorption of chromate ions or in the alternative hydroxyl ions from water or of both. If the latter view were true, we may observe "hydrolytic adsorption" if the hydrogen ions in the second layer can be replaced by a cation from a neutral solution of a salt *e.g.*, sodium chloride we will have an acid extract.

(2) The order of adsorbability of the cations is

The adsorbability of lead ions is the strongest amongst the cations. It is also very probable that besides the lattice energy of the ions, there are other factors such as the energy of hydration of the surface or of the ion which determine the intensity of adsorption, *i.e.*, the work necessary to separate an ion from the surface to the interior of the solution.

(3) The order of adsorption of anions is probably

The adsorption of chromate is probably the strongest.

(4) The constituent ions of a precipitate are very strongly adsorbed by it. Lead ions being so largely adsorbed as to reverse the charge. This observation suggests the possibility of preparing electrically neutral precipitates. As pointed out above, experiments with electrically neutral lead chromate will enable us to have a better idea of the intensity of adsorption of the different ions. The great intensity of adsorption of the constituent ions is in agreement with the views set forth in a previous paper.

(5) It is of great interest to note that the adsorption of the constituent ions does not consist simply in the exchange of an ion in the crystal lattice with an ion in the solution, as assumed by Paneth. Ions are actually fixed on the surface imparting a charge to it and the type of adsorption considered by Paneth cannot explain the observations recorded here.

(6) Fajans's suggestion that there is a parallelism between the intensity of adsorption of an ion and the solubility of the salt of the adsorbed ion and the ion

with opposite sign in the precipitate is not tenable as the nitrate ion is adsorbed more strongly than the iodide or sulphate.

The method of treatment developed here is capable of other interesting applications.

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORY
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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